

Fostering Resilience: An In-depth Investigation into the Dynamics of Growth and Development in Slum Children

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ABSTRACT

The goal of the study is to understand the socio-economic and educational circumstances of Slum dwellers in the Rajshahi City Corporation. The study was carried out in the Jahaj Ghat area, which is located on the Padma River. 31 street children were chosen to collect data at random from the vulnerable slum. Interviews and questionnaires were conducted with the kids and their family heads. The finding reveals that the households are at significant risk related to housing, shelter, sanitation, water, social security, education, health, and livelihood troubles. Finally, the study recommended resolving the existing problems which will empower the parents of the slum dwellers to provide adequate support for their children to continue schooling.

INTRODUCTION

A large city's impoverished neighborhood has long been a focal point for social and economic problems. The UN has used the word (Slum) to raise awareness of how critical urban issues are and to strengthen its capacity to draw resources to address the problem[1]. The high rate of crime and juvenile delinquency, as well as the widespread poverty, inadequate housing, bad sanitation, and society, are just a few examples. Slums are areas of cities with densely populated, neglected housing with traits of social isolation and hatred. This dynamic kind of globalization is largely responsible for the rapid urban population increase, the urbanization of poverty, and the spread of slums[2]. As a result, it is important to comprehend the many ways that globalization has affected low-income and impoverished urban inhabitants on both an individual and a community level. In most developing-nation cities, slums or informal settlements are a regular sight[3]. Policymakers, planners, and architects' widely held belief that it is the only method for delivering housing has been severely questioned by its function. Fast population expansion has the potential to make most urban issues worse. Delaying population expansion has several benefits, including better land and water management, less strain on ecosystems and natural resources, and more fair energy distribution in cities. Squatter settlements and slums are typified by cramped living arrangements, unclean surroundings, and a dearth of necessities including water, sanitary facilities, and trash disposals[4]. Slums typically develop haphazardly on privately or publicly owned unoccupied property. Slum houses are typically constructed with materials like bamboo, tin shed houses, straw leaves, gunny bags, and polythene paper for their walls and roofs. People's health is a worry, particularly for those who live in impoverished areas in any state or nation[5]. Their lives are vulnerable to hazards in the event of diseases and their treatment due to the restricted healthcare resources available to them. The most significant areas where urban poverty offers a significant risk are those related to housing, shelter, sanitation, water, social security, education, health, and the livelihoods of vulnerable populations including women, children, and the elderly in addition to their unique needs[6]. Slums are being created because of rapid urbanization and industrialism, which is pushing people to live in crowded, inhumane conditions in metropolitan regions. Slum residents have a variety of tribulations, hardships, and miseries related to necessities, such as social, constitutional, and economic rights. More particularly inhabitants in housing, food consumption, drinking water, sanitation, healthcare, education, jobs, income patterns, security and social standing, economics, and government support One of the challenges in modern towns is slum problems[7]. Even if the shanty towns of developed cities are evolving, a slum-free metropolis is unachievable. The urban population's proportion of impoverished individuals and slum residents is steadily rising. Although society structure and other causes might be to blame for this, it is recognized that the slum's physical, educational, economic, social, and environmental conditions are detrimental to both the residents and those inhabitants who do not live there. This is explicitly referred to as slums, which are all regions with extremely high population

densities and low-quality housing construction materials. Poor quality water supply and drainage systems, insufficient movement roads, an inadequate garbage collection system, a high percentage of residents earning a living from the unorganized economy, people living in substandard conditions, hunger, and malnutrition among the populace, dilapidated educational facilities, a high percentage of school dropouts, and occasionally the inability of children to complete primary education. Over half of the world's population now lives in urban areas due to the rapid growth of these populations worldwide. This half of the world's population lives in several developing nations. This growth has, in certain developing countries, involved a greater proportion of rural migration to informal settlements around cities, also referred to as "slums"; these densely populated urban areas are marked by subpar housing and inadequate living conditions. Densely populated urban regions are marked by subpar housing, a dearth of suitable living quarters and public amenities, as well as the accommodation of a sizable number of unofficial residents with often precarious housing arrangements with a tenure that is typically unstable[8]. Nowadays slums are a problem for urban citizens but more and more research activity can find a solution to the troubles[9]. Slum dwellers are experiencing dangerous health and sanitary insufficiency they need more domestic and international assistance[10]. Urban and local slums are not aware of government and leaders' roles. They should teach about moral and political awareness to take part in electoral and participatory action to make them good citizens and help the government to ensure good governance[11].

Objectives

- To find out the socio-economic conditions of slum children`s families in the selected area
- To access the educational status of school-going children in the slums.
- To identify the factors affecting the education of the children.
- To find out the problems faced by the slum children of the Rajshahi City corporation area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This paper aims to close this gap by examining pertinent resilience-based program design, implementation, and assessment challenges. To shed light on potential theoretical avenues for encouraging positive adaptation, a brief discussion of risk and resilience dynamics is provided[12]. Preventive program design trends that emphasize ecological pathways to behavioral and environmental change are highlighted. There is a little task on the selected areas. People on the River bank lead a poor life and are limited to pursuing their education as like as the rest places. Most individuals practice good hygiene, however, it can be challenging to do so because of the financial crisis and a lack of services[13]. Due to financial hardships or shortcomings in the educational system, children who are compelled to leave school and enter the workforce are deprived of the opportunity to acquire the skills and information required to realize their greatest potential. The primary victims of fundamental

rights are street children, domestic child laborers, and minors employed in hazardous jobs[14]. There are also some works on the topic of primary education in Bangladesh. In the setting of Bangladesh, one of the main obstacles to the advancement of human development is the widespread lack of basic education among the populace, particularly the rural poor and slum dwellers.[15]. In the intricate tapestry of urban living, slum children navigate a complex web of challenges that profoundly influence their growth and development. This literature review delves into the dynamics of fostering resilience in slum children, aiming to illuminate the multifaceted factors that contribute to their growth despite adverse conditions. Given the high morbidity rate in the group under study, it was determined that those with lower socioeconomic status would have different hygienic and health issues[16]. Slum regions are a widespread occurrence not just in Bangladesh but also globally. These are the result of the cultural and economic factors inside a certain social system that impede the moral, social, mental, and physical growth of the people[17]. A major development concern of the twenty-first century is the health and rights of people residing in urban slum settlements against the backdrop of rising dangers and disasters caused by climate change. However, because there is inadequate access to clean water, education, and a suitable sanitation system, the conditions in slum areas are far from adequate for them[18]. Although there are several research based on the slum dwellers in Bangladesh. There is very little work on our selected areas. The recent paper may reach the apex of success in raising awareness in the slum. The children can not afford basic education because of economic assistance[19]. So, this research paper will shed light on development of the slum children in education and their mental growth.

METHODOLOGY

A combination of qualitative and quantitative analysis went into the design of the study. To create a quality report, both quantitative and qualitative methods are required. A decent report cannot be produced with only one technique. The main methodology used in this study was a field survey with a scheduled set of structured interviews. The primary components of social research methodology include data gathering techniques, statistical analysis, tests, and study areas as well as sampling and testing. The respondents and the head of their family provided the study's data directly. Data for the year 2023 was gathered during 1-5 December. For data scrutinize and analysis, Microsoft Office Home and Student (2019) was utilized.

RESEARCH RESULT

4.1 Socio-economic conditions of the slum dwellers

As previously indicated, the primary participants in this study are youngsters living in slums. In this instance, 48% of respondents are female and 52% of respondents are male. We have selected the children from the slum who can understand standard questions.

Figure 1. The figure shows the age of the sample children.

4.2 The variation of ages in the selected children's parents

	Age Range	Category	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Father</i>	25-31	A	3	10%
	32-40	B	18	58%
	41-50	C	9	29%
	51-60	D	1	3%
<i>Mean age:</i> 37.54			Total: 31	100%
<i>Mother</i>	22-31	A	16	51%
	32-40	B	10	33%
	41-50	C	5	16%
<i>Mean age:</i> 31.19			Total: 31	100%

Table 1. The table shows the Children's Parents' ages.

Ten percent of fathers fall into Category A, fifty-eight percent fall into Category B, twenty-nine percent fall into Category C, and three percent fall into Category D. In this instance, the age ranges for categories A, B, C, and D are respectively, "25 to 31," "32 to 40," "42 to 50," and "51 to 60..." 18. P a g e 33% of moms are between the ages of 32 and 40, 16% are between the ages of 41 and 50, and 51% of mothers are between the ages of 22 and 31. The data indicates that the guardians in the slums are young. The Father's mean age is 37.54 whereas the mother's is 31.19. consequently, they can earn and spend for their family members. They are also capable of getting their children to school as usual.

Figure 2. Indicates the educational qualification of the slum Parents.

In this context, literate fathers are those who can write or sign their names. In this case, 42% of fathers have completed their primary label or less, 23% are in the secondary and higher category, and 32% of the fathers are literate, 3% are illiterate. On the other hand, 48% (mother) have completed elementary education or less, 36% have completed secondary education or higher, and 16% are literate because they can write or sign their name. It is good news that there is not an illiterate single mother.

Figure 3. The figure clarified the occupation of the slum's parents.

Day laborers make up 19% of the dads of children living in slums. 19% of the people working here are van drivers, 7% pull rickshaws, 10% are auto drivers, 13% own small enterprises, 7% work in the service industry, 3% are tailors, 3% are woodworkers, 3% are barbers, and 16% are unemployed. Housewives make up 58% of the moms of slum children in Rajshahi City Corporation's slum areas. Being a maidservant or doing household chores is

one of mothers' primary jobs. Domestic workers make up 26% of the mothers. 10% of mothers work in the beauty industry, and 6% work during the day.

Figure 4. It provides the family structure of the selected participants.

According to the figure, 23% of families consist of one to three people, 58% of families consist of four or five people and 19% of families consist of six to ten people. It means that poor people hold bigger families.

Figure 5. The figure indicates the income level of the families.

The respondents' total annual family incomes are categorized into four. Families fall into four categories: 45% fall into 4200-9700, 19% fall into 10000-15300, 33% fall into 15500-21000, and 3% fall into 21100-26500. The slum dwellers cannot manage enough money. Only 3% can afford their life to maintain a medium life standard.

4.3 The educational perspective of the slum children

Most people have lived in urban regions for the first time in human history in 2007, as the world rapidly becomes more urbanized. It is predicted that by 2030, there will be 4.9 billion people living in cities and 28 million fewer people living in rural areas[12]. We contend that communities and governments managing urban slums face unique challenges because of the very nature of slum life, which makes it challenging to attain improvements in living standards through marginal investments in housing, health care, or infrastructure alone[8]. In Bangladesh, most of the educated populous does not pursue effective research to ensure quality education. Policy-makers must take effective assistance to run good education.

Figure 6. Educational institutions in the slums.

Children in public or MPO schools read 48% of the time. Children read at private madrasha for 26% of them, private schools for 13% of them, and non-profit-run schools for 13% of them. This ensures that most of the children go to public schools.

Figure 7. The trends of attending the school of the slum children.

Of the children enrolled in school, 29% attend regularly, 26% are not regular, and 45% attend three days a week. The primary cause of irregular school attendance is illness. Most young girls are required to perform household

chores. The other two issues that girls face when they choose not to attend school are security and distance. Many of the kids living in slums work for pay to provide for their families.

1. The problems that hinder education in slum children

Numerous variables negatively impact the education of children. One of the biggest issues facing children's education is poverty, and in my findings, poverty is the source of all issues. Their parents lack the funds to purchase wholesome food. As a result, their children are unable to develop mentally and physically. Due to financial constraints, school-age children from slum areas are unable to purchase educational resources or hire additional tutors. In addition, parents' disinterest in school and a lack of drive, security, supervision, and child labor have a poor impact on children's educational outcomes. They are therefore far from receiving a top-notch education. The students attending the school Children in Rajshahi City Corporation's slum regions deal with a variety of issues. The slum neighborhoods' surroundings are extremely unhygienic. The slums' sanitation infrastructure is subpar. Because of their poverty, children are not receiving the appropriate care when they are ill. Young people are becoming involved in criminal activity. Drug misuse uses children as a conduit. In slum regions, child labor is another major issue. Many kids work in hazardous jobs to provide for their families. Numerous kids must perform household chores.

RECOMMENDATION

Following issue identification and a thorough assessment of Rajshahi City Corporation's impoverished regions, the following suggestions could be put into practice:

- In addition to enhancing the current ones' construction, the government, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) should build more elementary schools in and near Rajshahi City Corporation's slum regions.
- Children from poor neighborhoods should get Tiffins when they go to school.
- Special orientation initiatives should be implemented by the government and non-governmental groups to increase public understanding of the significance of enrolling children in preschool, primary, and secondary education.
- The government and non-governmental organizations should implement special orientation programs to raise public awareness and encourage school children's nutrition.
- The government ought to start by addressing the living conditions of people living in slums, as well as the utilities, health, and education systems.

- The municipal government of Rajshahi City Corporation must create a slum area drainage and sewer infrastructure as well as enhance solid waste management.
- The government should take action to ensure that liquid waste is disposed of safely by building new drains and maintaining and cleaning existing ones.
- There should be relationships both inside and between the government, non-governmental groups, and private organizations that assist slum inhabitants for the program to be successful.
- We advise more research to yield fruitful outcomes that will assist policymakers in assisting slum inhabitants.

CONCLUSION

Slum life is defined as a subhuman existence devoid of basic constitutional rights. Based on observations, feedback from residents, school-age children, local government employees, and historical data, it is evident that both school-age children and slum dwellers lack access to essential basic rights such as decent housing and health care, employment opportunities, sanitary facilities, education, and so forth. The facilities that school-age children need to continue their studies are inadequate. Most of the time, these kids live with sickness. These kids are living in extremely unhygienic conditions that are completely inappropriate for them. The slum sections of Rajshahi City Corporation had poor socioeconomic and infrastructure conditions. We also noticed that the communities are nearly the same in terms of socioeconomic position, housing, utility services, and political standing, as well as in terms of health. However, there are some noticeable differences in terms of housing quality, education, and monthly income.

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REFERENCES

- A. Gilbert, "The return of the slum: Does language matter?," *Int J Urban Reg Res*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 697-713, Dec. 2007, doi: 10.1111/j.1468-2427.2007.00754.x.
- S. Khan, D. Rathore, A. Singh, R. Kumari, and P. Malaviya, "Socio-economic and environmental vulnerability of urban slums: a case study of slums at Jammu (India)," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11356-023-30630-5.
- D. Roy, M. H. Lees, B. Palavalli, K. Pfeffer, and M. A. P. Slood, "The emergence of slums: A contemporary view on simulation models," *Environmental Modelling and Software*, vol. 59. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 76-90, 2014. doi: 10.1016/j.envsoft.2014.05.004.
- K. Rahman, M. Muhibbullah, and M. S. Islam, "Socio-economic Status of Slum Dwellers: A Case Study of Uttara Periphery, Dhaka." [Online]. Available: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/307856789>
- T. Izutsu, A. Tsutsumi, A. M. Islam, S. Kato, S. Wakai, and H. Kurita, "Mental health, quality of life, and nutritional status of adolescents in Dhaka, Bangladesh: Comparison between an urban slum and a non-slum area," *Soc Sci Med*, vol. 63, no. 6, pp. 1477-1488, Sep. 2006, doi: 10.1016/J.SOCSCIMED.2006.04.013.
- T. U. Zaman, "The Impact of Growth and Development of Slums on the Health Status and Health Awareness of Slum Dwellers Article in," 2018. [Online]. Available: www.ijmrhs.com
- B. Hossain, "Do the Slum Dwellers Enjoy the Basic Constitutional and Economic Rights as a Citizen in Bangladesh?"
- B. Marx, T. Stoker, and T. Suri, "The economics of slums in the developing world," *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 187-210, Sep. 2013, doi: 10.1257/jep.27.4.187.
- M. A. Hossain, A. Islam, and M. Khatun, "Unlocking Student Creativity and Research Potential in Bangladesh: The Crucial Role of Policy Makers in Breaking Deadlocks," *International Journal of Applied Research and Sustainable Sciences (IJARSS)*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1-16, 2023, doi: 10.59890/ijarss.v1i1.256.
- Md. A. Hossain, "Social Media a Concern for Foreign Relationships with Neighbor Countries," *International Journal of Applied Research and Sustainable Sciences*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 295-306, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.59890/ijarss.v1i4.1038.

- M. A. Hossan, A. Islam, and M. Khatun, "Empowering Democracy in Bangladesh: A Roadmap for Enhancing Voter Engagement," 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://ijssh.ielas.org>
- M. Bagheri, "The Challenge of Slums: Socio-Economic Disparities," *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, pp. 410-414, 2013, doi: 10.7763/ijssh.2012.v2.136.